

DTU

Mid-infrared OCT for non-destructive sub-surface inspection and in-line production monitoring

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4. airCode, Bismarckstr. 142, 47057 Duisburg, Germany
5. NKT Photonics A/S, Blokken 84, 3460 Birkerød, Denmark

OCT used for non-destructive measurement

Medic and bio research : [1]

Ophthalmology: glaucoma

Dermatology: vasodynamic imaging of vessels,
detect cancerous cell

OCT images from hand palm generated with the UHR-OCT system and the green delineations marking the surface tracing performed

N. M. Israelsen, et al, "The value of ultrahigh resolution OCT in dermatology - delineating the dermo-epidermal junction, capillaries in the dermal papillae and vellus hairs", *Biomedical Optics Express* **9** (2018)

[1] J. Walther, et al, "Optical coherence tomography in biomedical research", *Analytical Bioanalytical Chem* **400**, 2721–2743 (2011).

OCT used for non-destructive measurement

Non-destructive test:

Art : detect forgery [2], help paint conservation [3]

Industry: measured defect, topology, thickness of material [4]

Agrifood: control quality of the food [5]

OCT image of an area of a painting where there is one layer of old varnish, and a layer of new varnish was applied on top of the old varnish.[3]

Simplified painting cross-section

[2] S. Kim, et al, "Investigation of craquelure patterns in oil paintings using precise 3D morphological analysis for art authentication", PLOS ONE 17, e0272078 (2022)

[3] H. Liang, et al, "En-face optical coherence tomography - a novel application of non-invasive imaging to art conservation", Optics Express 13, 6133 (2005)

[4] T. Will, et al, "Prediction of electrical resistance of laser-welded copper pin-pairs with surface topographical information from inline post-process observation by optical coherence tomography", The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology 125, 1955-1963 (2023)

[5] I. V. Meglinski, C. Buranachai and L. A. Terry, "Plant photonics: application of optical coherence tomography to monitor defects and rots in onion" Laser Physics Letters 7, 307-310 (2010)

ZDZW and TURBO projects

Main goals:

- Waste reduction
- Objective zero defects
- Improved quality control
- Increase life of product

→ In line monitoring

→ Non-destructive testing

NORBLIS data base

A solution for non destructive inspection

Spectral domain OCT

MIR wavelength : $\lambda_0 \sim 4\mu m$

Axial resolution : $\Delta z = \frac{2 \ln 2}{\pi} \times \frac{(\lambda_0)^2}{\Delta \lambda} \sim 10\mu m$

Transversal resolution: $\Delta x \sim 30\mu m$

Sensitivity 60 dB – 3kHz A-scan rate

N. M. Israelsen, et al, "Real-time high-resolution mid-infrared optical coherence tomography", Light: Science & Applications **8** (2019)

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Manufacturing example 1 – Resin 3D print

Material : 3D printed Resin
 Size: 10 mm³
 Holes size : 0.4 mm²
 Manufacturer : SKYLAB

(a) Edge of the cube

(b) En face view

3d visualisation

Manufacturing example 2 – Ceramic 3D print

Material : 3D printed Alumina
 Size: 5 mm³
 Holes size : 0.13X0.082 mm²
 Manufacturer : LITHOZ
 Sintered state

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Sintered state

(c) En face view

Photographs for documentation

In line monitoring of manufacturing

ZDZW the challenge

- High performance prints
- Aerospace components
- Medical components
- Industrial components

<https://lithoz.com/en/>

<https://lithoz.com/en/>

Different states of the component during production:

Green bodies → Preconditioned components → Debinded components → Final sintered components

In line monitoring of manufacturing

Material : 3D printed Alumina
 Size: 19.77X4.96X2.56 mm³
 Defect size : 0.8 mm³
 Manufacturer : LITHOZ
 Green state

Green, printing method (a) Surface

Green, printing method (b) Surface

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